

Syntheses of Furano Compounds. Part XXII. Condensed Derivatives of γ -Brazan

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γ -Brazan has been succinoylated in the benzene nucleus at the 10-position and the product has been converted into isodinaphthylene oxide. A synthesis of coumarono-(2',3'-2,1)phenanthrene and the related quinone has been effected.

It has been shown that acylation of 2,3-benzodiphenylene oxide (β -brazan) and 3,4-benzodiphenylene oxide (α -brazan) leads to substitution in the naphthalene nucleus'. It is now found that in the succinoylation of 1,2-benzodiphenylene oxide (γ -brazan) (I) in nitrobenzene solution, the substitution takes place in the benzene nucleus at the 10-position. This orientation was arrived at by oxidation of the γ -ketonic acid (II) to γ -brazan-10-carboxylic acid (III) which proved identical with an authentic specimen synthesised in the following manner.

(I) : R=H; R'=H.

(II) : R=COCH₂CH₂COOH; R'=H.

(III) : R=COOH; R'=H.

(IV) : R=Me; R'=COOH.

(V) : R=Me; R'=H.

(VI) : R=CH₂CH₂CH₂COOH; R'=H.

(VIII) : R=H.

(IX) : R=CHO.

(X) : R=CH₂CO.COOH.

p-Toloxoxyacetophenone (VII) on cyclodehydration^{2,3} with phosphoric anhydride in benzene gave 5-methyl-3-phenylcoumarone (VIII) which was next formylated⁴ to the 2-formyl derivative (IX). The aldehyde was converted into 3-phenyl-5-methylcoumarone-2-pyruvic acid (X) *via* the related azlactone. Acid-catalysed cyclodehydration^{5,6} of the acid gave 10-methyl- γ -brazan-5-carboxylic acid (IV) which was decarboxylated and oxidised to γ -brazan-10-carboxylic acid (III).

1. Papers in the press.

2. Davies and Middleton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 822.

3. Chatterjea, *Science & Culture*, 1958, 24, 40.

4. Buu Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1955, 3688.

5. Geissmann and Tess, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 514.

6. Birch and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 503.

The above mentioned γ -ketoic acid was reduced to the butyric acid (VI) and then cyclized to furnish a single ketone (XI). The structure of the ketone has been established by its conversion to isodinaphthylene oxide (XII).

It should be noted that had the succinylation taken place in the naphthalene nucleus at the expected 3-position, the benzologation would have led to the coumaronophenanthrene (XIII) which was synthesised by the same sequence of reactions adumbrated above. Thus phenoxy-2-acetonaphthone, prepared from phenol and 2-bromoacetylnaphthalene, was first converted into the coumarone (XV) and then covered into the pyruvic acid (XVII) by way of the aldehyde (XVI) and the related azlactone. The cyclodehydration of the pyruvic acid was attended with decarboxylation, affording the coumaronophenanthrene (XIII) directly. The structure of the compound was established by its oxidation to the related phenanthraquinone which was characterised by the preparation of the quinoxaline derivative (XVIII).

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

(XIV)

(XV): R=H.
 (XVI): R=CHO.
 (XVII): R=CH₂COCOOH.

(XVIII)

EXPERIMENTAL*

10- β -Carboxypropionyl- γ -brazan.—A solution of γ -brazan⁷ (1.1 g.) and succinic anhydride (0.7 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (15 ml) was cooled to 0° and treated with stirring with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 g.). The mixture was kept at 0° for 2 days and then treated with HCl (dil.) and nitrobenzene removed by steam distillation. The bluish pink

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

7. Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1956, 38, 339.

crystalline residue crystallised from acetic acid in bluish prisms, *m.p.* 206-207°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 4.6. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 75.5; H, 4.4%).

Oxidation.—The above ketonic acid (0.2 g.) was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and treated on the water bath with a 1% solution of $KMnO_4$ (40 ml). When the colour of the permanganate was discharged, the mixture was filtered hot and acidified to yield *γ-braza-10-carbozylic acid*, *m.p.* >320°. (Found: C, 77.5; H, 3.9. $C_{17}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 77.9; H, 3.8%).

Isodinaphthylene Oxide.—A suspension of the foregoing ketonic acid (1.0 g.) in toluene (30 ml) was reduced with zinc amalgam (20 g.) for 72 hours. The pinkish toluene layer was separated, the solvent removed, and the residue crystallised from acetic acid. The unchanged acid (0.2 g.) that crystallised was filtered and the filtrate on dilution with water gave a semisolid mass. 10,3'-*Carboxypropyl-γ-braza* (VI) had a poor crystallising habit and was obtained with difficulty from acetic acid as colorless crystals; *m.p.* 130°. (Found: C, 78.6; H, 5.5. $C_{20}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 79.0; H, 5.2%).

The crude acid (0.5 g.) was treated with polyphosphoric acid (25 g.) and stirred for 3 hours at 140-50°. The acid mixture was poured into water, extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution washed with alkali. The neutral ketone, 9-keto-9,10,11,12-tetrahydroisodinaphthylene oxide was again obtained as a semisolid which furnished an orange-red 2,4-DNP (from acetic acid). It darkened and decomposed above 287°. (Found: N, 11.8. $C_{26}H_{18}O_5N_4$ requires N, 12.0%).

The crude ketone (0.2 g.) was reduced with $LiAlH_4$ (0.05 g.) in ether solution in the usual manner and the product dehydrogenated with palladised charcoal (0.1 g., 10%) for 1 hour. The product was distilled in vacuum and the solid (0.06 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates, *m.p.* 156-57°, alone or on admixture with an authentic sample of isodinaphthylene oxide; the mixed *m.p.* with *β*-dinaphthylene oxide, *m.p.* 159°, was depressed to 110°. (Found: C, 89.7; H, 4.6. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{12}O$: C, 89.6; H, 4.5). λ_{max}^{KCl} 253 (log ϵ , 4.73), 262 (log ϵ , 4.91), 284 (log ϵ , 4.40), 345 (log ϵ , 4.35), and 366 μ (log ϵ , 4.22).

p-Tolyloxyacetophenone.—A mixture of *p*-cresol (10.8 g.), phenacyl bromide (19.9 g.), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (40 g.) in dry acetone (120 ml) was refluxed for 4 hours. The mixture was filtered, the residue washed with acetone, and the acetone removed. The resulting viscous liquid was dissolved in ethanol and cooled. Brownish crystals of the phenoxy ketone (16.1 g.) was obtained which on recrystallisation provided a pale yellow solid, *m.p.* 68° (lit.⁸ *m.p.* 68°).

3-Phenyl-5-methylcoumarone.—The above ketone (5.0 g.) was dissolved in benzene (100 ml), treated with P_2O_5 (15 g.), and the mixture refluxed for 12 hours on the water bath. After decomposition with iced water, the benzene layer was separated and the solvent removed, affording the coumarone as a solid (3.0 g.) which crystallised from EtOH in prisms, *m.p.* 63-64°. (Found: C, 86.2; H, 5.9. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{12}O$: C, 86.5; H, 5.8%). The compound is described in literature⁹ (different method of preparation) as a liquid.

2-Formyl-3-phenyl-5-methylcoumarone.—A mixture of the above coumarone (3.0 g.), dimethylformamide (1.4 g.), and $POCl_3$ (2.5 ml) was refluxed on the water bath for 5 hours.

8. Kunokell, *Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 577.

9. Stoermer and Berthelme, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 857.

After cooling, the mixture was treated with a 10% solution (25 ml) of NaOH and heated on the water bath for 1 hour. The resulting darkish oil was extracted with ether, washed with water, and the solvent removed. The crude aldehyde (3.0 g.) was converted into the corresponding azlactone by heating with a mixture of hippuric acid (3.0 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (1.5 g.), and acetic anhydride (10 ml) on the water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The mixture was cooled and the azlactone collected after addition of aqueous ethanol. The compound crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 260°. (Found: C, 78.4; H, 5.0; N, 3.8. $C_{15}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 78.7; H, 4.8; N, 3.7%).

3-Phenyl-5-methylcoumarone-2-pyruvic Acid.—The azlactone (3.0 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with a mixture of 10% solution of KOH (40 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) for 12 hours. Ethanol was removed by distillation; the residue was diluted with water and acidified. The brownish solid separating was collected, washed with hot water, and crystallised from acetic acid. The pyruvic acid was obtained as brownish prisms, m. p. 220-25°, yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 73.0; H, 4.8. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.7%).

Cyclisation.—The foregoing ketonic acid (1.2 g.) in acetic acid (50 ml) was treated with aqueous hydrobromic acid (8 ml, 48%) and the mixture refluxed for 24 hours. On cooling, 10-methyl- γ -brazan-3-carboxylic acid (IV) separated which crystallised in colorless needles, m. p. 305°. (Found: C, 82.6; H, 4.8. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 82.8; H, 4.7%). The methyl ester, prepared by the action of diazomethane, crystallised from methanol in colorless needles, m. p. 115-16°. (Found: C, 83.0; H, 5.1. $C_{19}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 83.2; H, 5.1%).

The acid on decarboxylation by heating with lime gave 10-methyl- γ -brazan which crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m. p. 75°. (Found: C, 87.5; H, 5.4. $C_{17}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.9; H, 5.2%). λ_{max}^{alc} 232 (log ϵ , 4.6), 240 (log ϵ , 4.69), 248 (log ϵ , 4.71), 273 (log ϵ , 3.95), 284 (log ϵ , 3.93), 312 (log ϵ , 4.31), 325 (log ϵ , 4.28), 334 (log ϵ , 3.97), and 341 m μ (log ϵ , 4.10). The picrate crystallised from ethanol in orange-yellow needles, m. p. 144°. (Found: C, 59.3; H, 3.4; N, 9.0. $C_{17}H_{12}O.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires C, 59.8; H, 3.2; N, 9.1%). The 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone derivative crystallised from benzene in an orange crystalline mass, m. p. 191°. (Found: N, 7.5. $C_{17}H_{12}O.C_{13}H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 7.7%).

On oxidation with a boiling 1% $KMnO_4$ solution (40 ml), 10-methyl- γ -brazan (0.2 g.) provided a very poor yield of the acid (III); most of the original product was recovered unchanged.

α -Phenoxy-2-acetonaphthone.—A mixture of 2-bromoacetylnaphthalene (16.0 g.), phenol (6.0 g.), and potassium carbonate (35 g.) in acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for 6 hours. The mixture was filtered and the acetone solution concentrated. α -Phenoxy-2-acetonaphthone (9.0 g.) crystallised from ethanol in prisms, m. p. 82-84°. (Found: C, 82.1; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 82.2; H, 5.4%).

3-(2-Naphthyl)coumarone.—The above ketone (8.5 g.) was dissolved in benzene (40 ml), treated with phosphoric anhydride (15 g.), and the mixture refluxed on the water bath for 9 hours. The product was worked up in the usual manner and the coumarone purified by distillation, b. p. 215°/2.5 mm, yield 4.1 g. (Found: C, 88.0; H, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{12}O$ requires C, 88.5; H, 4.9%). The picrate crystallised from ethanol in yellow plates, m. p. 144°. (Found: C, 59.5; H, 3.5. $C_{18}H_{12}O.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires C, 60.1; H, 3.2%).

3-(2-Naphthyl)coumarone-2-pyruvic Acid.—The foregoing coumarone (3.5 g.) was formylated by heating on a water bath with a mixture of ~~formyl~~ methylformamide (1.5 g.) and POCl_3 (2.2 ml) for 4 hours. On working up as usual, the aldehyde (XVI) was obtained as a darkish oil (3.5 g.) which solidified on keeping. The *aldehyde* crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 80° . (Found: C, 83.5; H, 4.5. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 83.8; H, 4.4%). The 2,4-DNP crystallised from acetic acid in deep red needles which decomposed without melting above 275° .

The aldehyde (3.0 g.) was converted into the related *azlactone* (3.5 g.) by ~~heating~~ the water bath with a mixture of sodium acetate (1.0 g.), hippuric acid (2.5 g.), and acetic anhydride (25 ml). The compound crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. $259-60^\circ$. (Found: N, 3.3. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 3.4%).

The azlactone (3.4 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling with a mixture of 20% KOH (50 ml) and EtOH (20 ml) for 22 hours. After removing EtOH, the residue was diluted and acidified to furnish the *pyruvic acid* (XVII) as a brown crystalline mass which crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish plates, m.p. $230-33^\circ$. The compound gave a positive ferric reaction. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 4.1. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.4; H, 4.2%).

Cyclisation.—The above ketonic acid (2.0 g.) in acetic acid (50 ml) was treated with 48% HBr (20 ml) and the mixture boiled for 9 hours. On cooling, a colorless crystalline mass of *coumarono-(2',3'-2',1)phenanthrene* separated. The compound (1.1 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 205° . (Found: C, 89.1; H, 4.7. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ requires C, 89.6; H, 4.5%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 227 (log ϵ , 4.57), 265 (log ϵ , 4.64), 300 (log ϵ , 4.13), 313 (log ϵ , 4.42), 327 (log ϵ , 4.45), 342 (log ϵ , 3.62), and 360 μ (log ϵ , 3.59). The *trinitrobenzene* derivative crystallised from EtOH in long yellow needles, m.p. 154° . (Found: C, 65.0; H, 3.4. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3$ requires C, 64.9; H, 3.1%). 2,4,7-*Trinitrofluorenone* derivative crystallised from benzene in dark orange needles, m.p. 218° . (Found: C, 68.2; H, 3.0. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires C, 67.9; H, 2.9%).

Oxidation.—To a boiling solution of the coumaronophenanthrene (0.2 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml) a solution of chromium trioxide (0.4 g.) in water (2 ml) was added and the mixture boiled for $1\frac{1}{2}$ minutes. The mixture was poured into water and the orange-red product was collected. The *quinone* crystallised from acetic acid in small dark red prisms, m.p. 260° (previous darkening and sintering). (Found: C, 79.6; H, 3.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 80.5; H, 3.3%). On condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine in acetic acid, the *quinazoline* derivative (XVIII) separated quickly, m.p. 232° . (Found: C, 84.5; H, 4.2. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_2$ requires C, 84.3; H, 3.8%).

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